

Online Media Perspective on Trans Jogja as a Public Service in Yogyakarta City with Code Modeling

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ABSTRACT

Transjogya buses are currently not optimal. This research to analyze public perceptions of the importance of Transyogya buses as public transportation in the Special Region of Yogyakarta. This research method uses qualitative research methods by collecting data from online news media, online magazines and other online news sources. The method used modelling coding is to use Nvivo12 software by capitalizing the code results to get analysis results. His research data, it can be seen that by analyzing the agenda setting theory which consists of the media agenda with an online media perspective, it shows that the problems that are often discussed by the mass media related to Transyogya Transportation are Bus Stop Problems, Transyogya Problems and Portable Bus Stop Problems.

INTRODUCTION

Transportation problems are something that needs attention. Almost all big cities in Indonesia struggle with complex traffic problems. One of them is the problem of transportation and infrastructure choices which leads to increased traffic congestion. One of the causes of traffic jams is the increase in the number of cars caused by the development of road infrastructure. The increase in the number of cars is in line with the increase in population because vehicles are needed to facilitate the transportation of passengers. Transportation facilities or means of transportation are needs that arise from economic, social, cultural and other activities (Nurmalita, 2000). Based on research that has been conducted (Kurniawan et al., 2021). Transportation problems in urban areas, especially in the Yogyakarta Urban Area, are caused first by the lack of adequate facilities and infrastructure in the Yogyakarta Urban Area. Second, there is low public awareness regarding the use of traffic facilities and road equipment. Then, in the Yogyakarta Urban Area, traffic demand management has not been implemented properly to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of traffic use and control traffic movements. Within the scope of these facilities and infrastructure problems, there are public transportation problems on Trans Yogya. As we know, the definition of transportation is the movement of people and/or goods from one place to another using vehicles in traffic, Transjogja urban transportation is a public passenger transportation system within the Yogyakarta Urban Area using public passenger vehicles in the form of buses (Peraturan Gubernur DIY, 2021).

The people of Yogyakarta and its surroundings are currently still being treated to the Trans Yogya Bus service which runs 18 routes, where these routes run almost most of the routes in the city of Yogyakarta. As we know, public transportation services aim to provide comfortable, timely, safe and cheap services to the community. The presence of public transportation is very beneficial for managing traffic and road transportation, because these facilities are very efficient in using road infrastructure. However, in reality, the need for public transportation in municipalities is currently the last option for carrying out their transportation activities. Now you can see that many Trans-Yogya buses only carry a few passengers, sometimes even no passengers. This indicates that some bus stops are rarely used. In the Jogja Daily (Sunarton, 2022b), general manager of PT Jogja Tugu Trans (JTT) Agus Adrianto said that the number of passengers on the Sahabat Trans Jogja bus was actually not optimal. The average load factor [passenger supply] is only about 25%, on some routes it is even lower. There are many factors that contribute to this.

One of them is the habit of using private cars and motorbikes, the number of which cannot be limited. At the opening of Trans Yogya, guards were waiting at the bus stop, now you could see lots of cannons. Even the payment system that used to be done at stations has now changed in transportation. This is due to the lack of public interest in using the Trans Yogya Bus mode as a mandatory mode of transportation. Another phenomenon is that several bus corridors have even been abolished because the service is very low, as seen in the Godean corridor. This corridor is now experiencing service restrictions to

meet the needs of public transportation in the area. According to Harian Jogja (Sunartono, 2022a), the Main Director took steps as a substitute for eliminating the Trans Jogja transportation service, he replaced it with the Bus Friends Service, where public transportation services are still served in the morning and afternoon. This timing is adjusted to suit passenger needs, because as long as Teman Bus operates, there are more passengers at both times. The Godean corridor is still there, only the hours are slightly reduced. Currently operating in the morning from 05.30 to 08.00 WIB and in the afternoon from 14.30 to 17.00 WIB.

The Government has made various efforts to modernize the Transyogya bus service in order to keep up with developments and progress over time, the first effort is an application service that makes it easier for transportation service users to find out information related to the Transyogya bus, the application service is the Trans Jogja application. The second effort is the implementation of low and very affordable prices by the DI Yogyakarta government so that people want to use this mode of transportation. 3,600 for the general public and Rp. 60 for students. The third effort is the introduction of the Friends of the Bus service, where the Indonesian Ministry of Transportation launched the Friends of the Bus program in Yogyakarta on December 31 2020. Friends of the bus is an abbreviation for economical, cheap, safe and comfortable transportation. Sahabat Bus Jogja offers wider routes than Trans Jogja. Sahabat Bus will serve three new corridors including Ngabean-Godean Culinary Park, Adisusipto-Pakem Airport and Condong Katur-UGM-Pakem Terminal with a total of 44 bus. Therefore, the training or fleet arrival time will be shorter, namely 5-10 minutes.

Of the many efforts that have been made by the Government, it turns out that there are still several vehicle fleets that still use this transportation service. On the other hand, the government and transportation activists continue to actively promote the use of public transportation as part of a lifestyle so that traffic management is carried out well. Followed by the disbursement of subsidy funds using a service purchasing system (a mechanism for purchasing urban transport services implemented by the Yogyakarta Regional Government for transport operators on a subsidized basis) grants (Peraturan Gubernur DIY, 2021) provided by the DIY Yogyakarta Provincial Government every year. From the data that has been retrieved (Tomi, 2019) with news entitled "IDR 81 Billion Subsidized, Trans Jogja Must 'Improve' on krjogja.com published on 02 Dec 2019, 13:23 WIB, that the Yogyakarta City Government has disbursed tens of billions for Trans Jogja public transport subsidies. The aim is to allocate subsidies, the main purpose of using subsidies. By distributing grants of that size, it was hoped that Transyogya urban transportation would be widely accepted by the general public, but what happened was the opposite. Demand for using public transportation is very low. Perception of public acceptance is one of the keys to successful implementation of transportation policies (Scade and Schlag, 2000). Therefore, this research tries to analyze public perceptions of the importance of Transyogya buses as land-based public transportation in Yogyakarta

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Coding Method

NVivo is one of the software developed from simple code to various systems to assist the methodology qualitative inquiry. To deepen the use of NVivo-NVivo2020 software, lecturers and reviewers need to discuss not only how to use the program but also design and analysis issues assessment, selection of methodology and analysis program(Jasmi, 2021). When collecting customer feedback, you highlight words or phrases that represent important (and recurring) themes in each response. These tags can be words, phrases, or numbers; We recommend using short words or phrases because they are easier to remember, skim, and organize. Coding qualitative research to explore common themes and concepts is part of thematic analysis, which is a subset of qualitative data analysis. Topic analysis extracts themes from text by analyzing the structure of words and sentences. For example, in objective hermeneutics and conversation analysis, researchers limit the use of specific data collection methods beyond recording everyday situations. In this case, the use of research methods includes the application of these methods to the interpretation of texts. The categorization process until the researcher finds a theory is shown in Figure 3 (Saldana, 2013). Goals of Coding in Qualitative Research The three main goals of the Coding Guide for Qualitative Research are:

1. Briefly discuss the tasks of coding, coding, and editing analytical notes during the process of collecting and analyzing qualitative data
2. Selected profiles profiles in different coding repertoire Analysis Methods usually applied to qualitative data and
3. Provide readers with resources, descriptions, examples, uses, and recommended exercises for coding and then analyzing qualitative data.

Figure 1. Coding Model Path to Theory Building for the Qualitative Inquiry Process

B. NVivo Software

Developed and distributed by QSR International, NVivo is one of the most popular and widely used software by social researchers. This software can run on any information system and perform advanced analysis of text, images, audio and video, web pages, social media, emails and data sets. Nvivo can perform barcoding, subject coding, Nvivo coding, and color coding to further improve research performance. NCapture plugin for collecting social media posts and importing them into the application. automatic coding of records such as survey responses. Visualization of findings. Questions that dig into data and test theories, search text, check word frequency, and create crosstabs. Easily share data with quantitative analysis applications. Collect data from mobile devices and import it into apps with Evernote.

METHODOLOGY

This research method uses qualitative research methods by collecting data from online news, online magazines and other online news. The analysis method used is the coding method using Nvivo12 software by capitalizing the code results to get the analysis results. This research method uses qualitative research methods by collecting data from online news, online magazines and other online news.

The method used is to use Nvivo software by capitalizing the code results to get analysis results. Data collection was carried out before the research, data was taken from daily online media, online media readings and other online social media. Meanwhile, the theory that will be used is Agenda Setting Theory. Agenda setting theory was first put forward by Mc Comb and Donald L. Shaw in Public Opinion Quarterly published in 1972 entitled The Agenda Setting Function of Mass media. The two experts stated that "if the media puts emphasis on an event, then the media will influence the audience to consider it important." This theory is based on the results of a study regarding the 1968 United States Presidential election. Agenda setting theory describes the magnitude of the influence of the media and its ability to "tell" what issues are important. The issues or individuals that the media chooses to publish, ultimately become the issues and individuals that thought and discussed by the public (Griffin, 2006).

The agenda setting approach begins with the assumption that the mass media filters the news, articles or writings that will be broadcast. This selection is carried out by those who are called gatekeepers, namely journalists, editors in chief and image editors. It is the gatekeeper who determines what news should be published and what should be hidden. Each issue is given a certain weight, whether it is published on the front page as a headline, or on the back page in a corner or whatever, whereas on television, how long it is broadcast, how many times it is shown, and so on. The highlighting of issues in the mass media is what is called the media agenda, which will correlate or relate to the public agenda, namely what the public is thinking and discussing (community salience) (Subiakto & Ida, 2012).

Agenda setting theory explains the purpose of the media in compiling the news conveyed to the public. In this way, the mass media unilaterally selects what is considered important. As with today's mass media, it is very difficult to prove the seriousness of media that displays news that covers both sides (McQuail, 1987). First, the media agenda itself must be prepared by the media crew. Second, the media agenda in some ways influences or interacts with the public agenda. Third, the political agenda, namely what political policy makers think is related to public policy or what is considered important by the public.

The indicators for the three agendas are; (1) media agenda: issues discussed by a media: Visibility: The amount and level of news prominence that can be seen from the location of the news and its length (time and space); level of prominence for the audience (audience salience): the relevance of the news content to the needs of the audience; valence (valence: the method of reporting and presentation of a topic or news. (2) public agenda: the public's instinct regarding the importance of an issue; familiarity: the degree of public awareness of a particular topic; personal salience: the relevance of individual interests with personal characteristics; favorability: consideration of whether one likes or dislikes a news topic. (3) political agenda: the public agenda influences political decision makers; support: favorable activities for the position of a particular news item; possible activities (likelihood action) : the possibility of the government carrying out what is implied; freedom of action: the value of activities carried out by the government.

RESEARCH RESULT

Public Transportation Services

Public transportation services are transportation systems provided by the government or private operators to serve the general public by providing transportation facilities that can be used by many people. The main aim of public transportation services is to provide easier, more affordable and efficient access for city or regional residents in making daily trips. The following are some of the main characteristics of public transportation services:

1. Access for the Public: Public transportation services are open to everyone regardless of social, economic status or background. This means anyone, including workers, students, parents, and tourists, can use the service.
2. Scheduled: Public transportation services usually operate based on a fixed schedule that is accessible to the public. This schedule allows passengers to plan their journey better.
3. Fixed Routes: Public transportation services usually have fixed routes that connect various places in a city or region. This route may include travel by bus, train, tram, ferry or other type of public transportation.
4. Affordable Costs: The costs of using public transportation are often more affordable than using private vehicles. This helps reduce the financial burden for many people and encourages the use of public transport.
5. Compliance with Safety Standards: Public transport operators are obliged to comply with strict safety standards to protect passengers and other road

users. This includes vehicle care and maintenance, passenger safety regulations, and driver training.

6. Support Sustainable Mobility: Public transportation services are often part of efforts to reduce traffic congestion, air pollution, and other negative environmental impacts that can be caused by private vehicles. They can also support sustainable mobility by promoting the use of more environmentally friendly transport.
7. Support for Infrastructure Improvement: Public transportation requires adequate infrastructure, such as stations, stops, lines and terminals. This can encourage investment in transport infrastructure that can improve the mobility and connectivity of a city or region.
8. Public transportation services can be of various types, including buses, trains, trams, public transportation, ferries, or a combination of various modes of transportation. The goal is to provide adequate transportation options for people so they can reach their destinations more efficiently and comfortably.

There are many perceptions that arise from the public, both users and non-users of Trans Jogja public transportation. From this point of view, more or less has been published in circulating online media. Both from national and local online media. This online media represents the public's point of view in assessing the Trans Jogja public transportation service.

Based on the news documents used as research objects, there are several arguments and perceptions. The objects of the news are as follows:

Table 4.1 Online Media Source Data

No	Media Name	News Title	Angel News
1	https://tirto.id/11-tahun-trans-jogja-pernah-rugikan-negara-anggaran-tabrak-4-pemotor-emzW	11 Years of Trans Jogja: Has Caused Losses to the State and Hit 4 Motorbikes	Incident complaints
2	https://www.kompasiana.com/nisaadnan/5a24b65ccf78db30c54d2032/aksesILI-kaum-disabel-dalam-cepatan-transportasi-umum-trans-jogja	Accessibility for Disabled People in Using TransJogja Public Transportation	Incident report
3	https://jogja.tribunnews.com/2021/07/18/begini-penjauhan-dinas-perbesar-diy-soal-bus-trans-jogja-berhenti-beroper	This is the DIY Transportation Department's explanation regarding the Trans Jogja Bus Stopping	Incident report

No	Media Name	News Title	Angel News
		Operation	
4	https://yogyakarta.kompas.com/read/2022/09/06/150359778/dishub-diy-pastikan-tak-ada-kenaikan-tarif-bus-trans-jogja	DIY Transportation Department Ensures There Will Be No Increase in Trans Jogja Bus Fares Page all	Incident report
5	https://www.dprd-diy.go.id/huda-tri-yudiana-sebaiknya-transjogja-gratis-buat-pelajar/	DIY DPRD Hopes Students Ride Trans Jogja for Free - Huda Tri Yudiana, ST	Incident Report
6	https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/434959-none-a34b925a.pdf	Effectiveness of Trans Jogja as a Public Service in the City of Yogyakarta	Incident Complaints
7	https://journal.unpak.ac.id/index.php/jimfe/article/view/3386	Expectations Of Users Of Trans Jogja Public Transportation Services	Incident complaints
8	https://bisnismuda.id/read/6185-phia/jadi-transportasi-umum-yogyakarta-se-oke-apa-sih-trans-jogja	So Yogyakarta public transportation, how good is Trans Jogja?	Incident Report
9	https://tirto.id/jogja-macet-saat-nataru-cermin-buruknya-transportasi-publik-gAp3	Jogja Congested During Nataru & Reflection of Poor Public Transportation	Incident Report
10	https://www.kompasiana.com/ikromzzzt/61d64bac2da2377e724e6842/kena-prank-dan-ghosting-jasateman-bus-kebelian-community-terhadap-transportasi-publik-pun-menurun-drastis	Affected by "Pranking" and "Ghosting" by Bus Friend Services, Public Trust in Public Transportation Has Declined Drastically	Incident complaints
11	https://ugm.ac.id/id	People still	Incident Complaints

No	Media Name	News Title	Angel News
	/berita/3298-community-masih-keluhkan-lamanya-time-tempuh-trans-jogja/	complain about the long travel time for Trans Jogja	
12	https://hmgp.geo.ugm.ac.id/2022/08/08/pengembangan-transit-oriented-development-tod-dalam-mewujudkan-kota-yang-efficient/	Development of Transit Oriented Development (TOD) in Creating an Efficient City - Development Geography Student Association	Incident Report
13	https://jogjapolitan.arianjogja.com/read/2022/09/19/510/1112224/penum-pang-trans-jogja-only-049-persen-dari-user-angkutan-di-jogja	Trans Jogja passengers are only 0.49 percent of transport users in Jogja	Incident Report
14	https://www.krjogja.com/yogyakarta/1242531339/subsidi-besar-jasa-trans-jogja-besar-baik	Big Subsidies, Trans Jogja Services Must Be Good	Incident Complaints
15	https://dishub.jogjaprov.go.id/trans-jogja	Has Trans Jogja been effective?	Incident Complaints
16	https://www.kompasiana.com/divarabiah8904/639ae1ee08a8b54ae572bb72/tatkala-trans-jogja-bukanlah-andalan	When Trans Jogja is not a mainstay	Incident Complaints
17	https://www.starjogja.com/2018/09/27/trans-jogja-focus-cepatkan-jasa/	Transjogya Focuses on Improving Services	Incident report
18	https://www.kompas.id/baca/utama/2019/01/22/trans-jogja-belum-jadi-prioritas-di-jalan-raya	Trans-Jogja Not Yet a Priority on Highways	Incident Complaints

No	Media Name	News Title	Angel News
19	https://jogjapolitan.arianjogja.com/read/2022/12/13/512/1120255/transportasi-publik-di-diy-tak-laku-pengamat-perjual-akses-kendaraan-personal	Public Transportation in DIY Not Selling, Observer: Making Access to Private Vehicles Difficult!	Incident Complaints

Source: Researcher Data, 2023

From the online media results that have been collected above, they have been obtained and input into Nvivo12. Nvivo is a popular program and is widely used by social researchers. This software can be run on all information systems and can carry out advanced analysis of text, images, audio and video, web pages, social media posts, emails and datasets.

Nvivo can do coding, theme coding, NVivo coding and color coding stripes making research work better. NCapture add-on for collecting social media posts and bringing them into the program. automatic coding of datasets such as survey responses. Visualization of findings. Questions that examine data and test theories, search texts, study word frequencies, create cross-tabs. Easily exchange data with quantitative analysis programs. Collect data on mobile devices using Evernote, import into the program.

Perception is a person's view of a particular thing or event. Yogyakarta has public transportation which is used by the native people of Yogyakarta and its surroundings to carry out transportation activities. This public transportation is Transyogya public transportation. In this case, researchers conducted research related to online media perceptions regarding Transyogya public transportation services. The data taken in this research amounted to 19 online media that reported on Transyogya public transportation services. From the results of data collection and data processing using Nvivo12, the Word Frequency data processing results show that the 19 online media that discuss perceptions of public transport services most often are the word Halte which represents 558 words, Transyogya 361 words, Portabel 211 words and Bus 117. Based on the Word Frequency results The research data shows that all documents are related to each other in accordance with research discussions related to online media perceptions of TransYogya public transportation services. The following are the results of Word Frequency analysis using Nvivo12.

10. Trans Yogya focuses on improving service
11. New direction for Trans Yogya
12. Trans Yogya is not yet a priority on the highway
13. Effectiveness of Trans Yogya as a public service
14. Trans Yogya is not a mainstay
15. People complain about the long travel time for Trans Yogya
16. Bus Friends Breakthrough
17. Prospects for intelligent transportation
18. Expectations of users of public transportation services
19. Residents are invited to take the Trans Yogya

CONCLUSIONS

From the results of the analysis of agenda setting in online media, data collection and data processing using Nvivo12, the results obtained from online media's perspective on Trans Jogja as a public service in the city of Yogyakarta with coding modeling through Word Frequency data processing show that the 19 online media discuss the perception of public transport services most Many are the words Bus Stop which represents 558 Transyogya words 361 words, Portable 211 words and Bus 117. And what can be seen from the analysis of the agenda setting which consists of the media agenda with an online media perspective shows that the problem that is often discussed by the mass media regarding Transyogya Transportation is Problem Bus Stops, Transyogya Problems and Portable Bus Stop Problems.

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